

Review

Impact of Nursing Care in Comorbid Patients with Cardiovascular Diseases

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Abstract

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With the improvement of living standards, people have more and more physical health problems. Most prominent among them are high-risk cardiovascular diseases (CVDs). Effectively improving treatment and accelerating recovery in cardiac patients has become a social issue. A number of studies have proven that the significant social and economic changes in our society affect personal health. So, they lead to development of various concomitant chronic diseases. The main CVDs risk factors are: arterial hypertension, abnormalities in fat metabolism, smoking, alcohol abuse, diabetes mellitus, obesity, low physical activity, psycho-emotional stress, unhealthy diet and others. Reducing or eliminating the impact of certain risk factors can significantly reduce the risk of developing ischemic heart disease (IHD). We need coordinated efforts, while providing inpatient and outpatient care, to educate and encourage the patient to change to a healthier lifestyle. An important task of cardiac nurses is to act preventively in the long term. They need knowledge, skills and resources to enable them to function as leaders in patient health education. In addition to the specific knowledge of cardiovascular health care, cardiac nurses must implement evidence-based practice and effective personalized care. Effective communication, information delivery, and patient education are at the core of practical preventive cardiology.

Keywords: Cardiovascular Diseases (CVDs), Comorbid patients, Impact, Nurse, Nursing care

INTRODUCTION

CVDs remain the largest cause of mortality worldwide, despite the spectacular decline in age-specific cardiovascular mortality in Western societies over the past few decades (Capewell et al., 2011). Improved primary prevention and pharmacological treatment of cardiovascular risk factors have resulted in a lower risk of cardiovascular events and reduction in mortality (Capewell et al., 2011; O'Flaherty et al., 2013). As a result, the age at which people suffer their first cardiovascular event has increased and patients live longer after the CVD onset (Koopman et al., 2016). Consequently, more CVD patients have a longer life

expectancy and increasingly experience comorbid conditions, making this population of particular interest in the study of comorbidity. The presence of one or more concomitant chronic diseases is defined as comorbidity (Feinstein, 1967). Comorbidity can potentially lead to worse functional status, lower quality of life and even increased mortality (Barnett et al., 2012; Vos et al., 2015). Along with the effects on patients, the presence of multiple chronic diseases is also a challenge for healthcare systems, such as primary care, since they have traditionally been configured around individual diseases. This fragmented perspective can potentially

lead to conflicting medical advice and interacting drugs (Boyd et al., 2005). Nowadays, comorbidity tends to be considered the rule rather than exception, so increasing the awareness and improving guidelines for patients with comorbid conditions are critical for prevention of adverse health outcomes, increase in efficiency, and cost reduction. One of the first steps in this process is to assess CVD comorbidity prevalence and provide context for future research. Despite the large number of people with complex needs and recognized impact they have on health care, there is no current evidence on the prevalence of different combinations of comorbid conditions by gender and age. In addition, most studies examine two diseases at most, while CVD patients often have more than two comorbid conditions (Barnett et al., 2012; Wong et al., 2011; McMannus et al., Chamberlain et al., 2015).

Studies in the field prove that patients' discomfort during hospitalization before and after invasive cardiac procedures is reduced because they receive detailed information and guidance provided by the nurse. Nurses can assess patient needs during hospitalization, evaluate their knowledge and provide educational information, so that patients are empowered, have reduced feelings of discomfort during hospitalization and better quality of life after that (Kleisari et al., 2021).

CVDs account for a major proportion of diseases in the elderly population worldwide and have been a major cause of mortality in recent decades. The most common forms of cardiovascular disease are ischemic heart disease (IHD), cerebrovascular disease and hypertension. Myocardial infarction (MI) is one of the most severe IHD clinical forms. It is the leading cause of death and disability worldwide. MI is ischemic necrosis, death of a part of the heart muscle tissue due to insufficient blood and oxygen supply. It has great social importance because of the high disability and mortality it causes.

Heart attack (also known as myocardial infarction) is the death of the heart muscle from a sudden blockage of the coronary artery by a blood clot. Coronary arteries are the blood vessels that supply the heart muscle with blood and oxygen. Their blockage deprives the heart muscle of blood and oxygen, causing cardiac ischemia, in which the patient feels chest pain and pressure. If blood flow to the heart muscle is not restored within 20 to 40 minutes, its death becomes irreversible. Cardiac tissue continues to die for 6 to 8 hours, and after that point cardiac necrosis is usually complete. MI is one of the most important causes of death and disability worldwide. Coronary atherosclerosis is a chronic disease with stable and unstable periods. During unstable periods, as a result of an activated inflammatory process in the blood vessel wall, patients may experience MI.

Heart attack is usually observed in the active adult age (40-65 years), but in the last decade, due to an increase in its frequency, it is established and becomes more frequent at a younger age. In terms of morbidity and

gender-specific incidence, up to about 55-60 years of age, the male gender predominates. MI may be the result of a lifelong chronic disease, in some cases it may even be asymptomatic but in others it may be a catastrophic event leading to sudden death or severe hemodynamic collapse.

The incidence of this disease has increased in recent years and is a major social problem. Bulgaria ranks first in the number of heart attack patients. It mostly affects people around 45 to 65 years of age, but it can also significantly affect younger people. It leads to early disability and high mortality (Tomov, 1999; Tomov, 2003).

RESEARCH AREA

Thanks to the work of the World Health Organization (WHO) and international scientific societies, considerable experience has been gained in prevention and approaches to dealing with CVD. Several large projects related to risk factors and cardiac prevention have been implemented in Europe: INTERHEART, EUROASPIRE I, II, III, IV, V; EUROACTION; MONICA etc. (Kotseva et al., 2009; Kotseva et al., 2018; McGorrian et al., 2011; Wood et al., 2004).

Nurses, as well as other health professionals: rehabilitators, physiotherapists, nutritionists, psychologists, can carry out activities contributing to the successful prevention of cardiovascular diseases. They can provide health information, educate patients and their families about the principles of a healthy lifestyle and motivate them to actively cooperate in order to improve health and quality of life (Jennings et al., 2017; Ollisara et al., 2019).

Results from the international European program EUROASPIRE (European Action on Secondary and Primary Prevention by Intervention to Reduce Events) for prevention of cardiovascular risk show that regardless of the large number of medications for primary and secondary prevention of CVD, patients with or without IHD history do not reach target values for risk factors. The study was performed four times in the period 1997-2013, with 24 participating European countries, including Bulgaria. There is cumulative evidence on lifestyle, risk factors, and therapeutic outcomes of CVD patients and high-risk individuals receiving standardized treatment. The results are worrying, no trends for reducing risk factors have been established. More than half of the examined patients (56%) in the three stages of the EUROASPIRE study with proven IHD had arterial pressure values above the desired values, and only 55% of those treated for dyslipidemia, maintained lipid levels below the target values. More than 1/3 of IHD patients also have diabetes mellitus, and only 10% of them manage to control blood sugar below 6.1 mmol/L. A very important conclusion was made: more and more drugs are prescribed for the treatment of hypertension and

dyslipidemia, but effective measures are not applied to control the problems related to risk factors and unhealthy lifestyle (Kotseva et al., 2009; Kotseva et al., 2018).

At the same time, data from other studies support the conclusion that CVDs prevention is economically, socially, and humanely superior to any therapy. Researchers performed specific modeling to compare cardiovascular prevention with treatment in people aged 30 to 84 years who had different levels of risk, frequency of cardiac events, patterns of behavior, treatment, and mortality. They found that 44% of all deaths were due to heart diseases. Managing risk factors before an acute incident would prevent or delay 33% of deaths. In comparison, optimal medical treatment during an acute coronary event would reduce mortality by only 8% (Castellano et al., 2013; Nikolich-Zugich et al., 2016). Patients receiving traditional treatment showed poorer outcomes compared to patients using lifestyle change educational programs (OR 1.48 [95% CI, 1.17-1.88]). Prevention programs involving goal setting, self-monitoring, action planning, and feedback have shown improved healthy eating and physical activity among participants. These results were supported by other studies demonstrating the benefits of lifestyle change education, leading to better clinical outcomes and quality of life (Janssen et al., 2013; Karmali et al., 2014).

In 2017, Frederix et al. recommended the use of a comprehensive informational approach to CVDs prevention, including multiple components: risk assessment; counseling for physical activity and development of a training program; dietary nutrition counseling; control of risk conditions; psycho-social support and management; adherence to therapy; patient health education (2017). The challenge is motivating people to long-term adherence to positive lifestyle changes. Many patients report that they did not receive strong encouragement from doctors and other health professionals regarding prevention. The management of risk factors would have effective results with good motivation and appropriate health education. Good practices should be multiplied in health policies for all communities, with full participation of nurses and other specialists in multidisciplinary teams (Frederix et al., 2017).

Nowadays, comorbidity is considered to be the rule rather than the exception. In addition to the effects on individual patients, comorbidity presents additional challenges for health care systems. Despite the large number of patients with CVDs and comorbidity and the recognition of their effect on health care, current evidence is lacking on whether the prevalence of different combinations of comorbidities varies between men and women and how it changes over time. Results from studies along these lines can help researchers in the area identify relevant subgroups, inform them which comorbid conditions are most prevalent and may require prioritization, and target health care resources for

patients with multiple diseases.

The study by Buddeke et al. looked at two types of comorbidity: non-cardiovascular and cardiovascular (2019). Poor vision, diabetes, back/neck problems, osteoarthritis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and cancer were the most common non-cardiovascular conditions and were among the top five non-cardiovascular comorbid conditions in all CVD patient groups in the study. Of these, in age- and gender-adjusted analyses, diabetes, poor vision, and COPD were statistically significantly more prevalent in CVD patients compared to patients without CVD. In addition, asthma was also statistically more common in CVD patients. In stroke patients, prevalence of most comorbid conditions appeared to be slightly lower than in other patients. Epilepsy, however, was more common in stroke patients. Osteoarthritis was a very common comorbid condition, with a prevalence of 32% among heart failure (HF) patients. When all musculoskeletal conditions (back/neck problems, osteoarthritis, osteoporosis and rheumatoid arthritis) were grouped together, the percentage increased to 52%. The prevalence of a number of non-cardiovascular comorbid conditions appeared to be highest in HF patients compared to other cardiovascular conditions.

IHD is the most common cardiovascular comorbid condition in HF patients: 38%, peripheral arterial disease (PAD): 25% and stroke: 19%. In IHD patients, HF is the most common cardiovascular comorbidity. In age- and sex-adjusted analyses, all cardiovascular comorbid conditions were more prevalent in CVD patients compared to patients without CVD. HF patients had the highest prevalence of cardiovascular comorbid conditions, followed by those with PAD. 27% of HF patients had both cardiovascular comorbidity and musculoskeletal disease, compared to 18%, 16%, and 12% of patients with PAD, stroke, and IHD, respectively (Buddeke et al., 2019).

Previous studies confirmed the finding that comorbid conditions are particularly prevalent in HF patients (Chamberlain et al., 2015; van Oostrom et al., 2012; Sinnige et al., 2015; Buddeke et al., 2017). Another study in the Dutch population observed that HF patients had the highest prevalence of comorbidity (92%) compared to those with other CVD such as stroke (81%) and IHD (80%) (van Oostrom et al., 2012). In addition, HF patients more often have simultaneously cardiovascular and non-cardiovascular comorbidities. In the previous study, there was a high HF incidence combined with both a cardiovascular comorbid condition and musculoskeletal disorder, and HF combined with both a cardiovascular comorbid condition and asthma and/or COPD.

Studies investigating diseases with trinucleotide repeats are scarcer than studies investigating double diseases. However, a study by Sinnige et al. showed results in the same direction, with a high prevalence of HF-coronary artery disease-COPD and heart failure-

coronary artery disease-osteoarthritis (2015).

This confirms the finding from previous studies that poor vision, diabetes, back/neck problems, osteoarthritis, COPD and cancer are very common non-cardiovascular conditions among patients with HF, CVD and stroke (van Oostrom et al., 2012; Sinnige et al., 2015). These diseases are also the most common conditions in PAB patients. In addition, other diseases emerged that are the most common non-cardiovascular comorbidities in different age groups and affect men and women similarly. However, musculoskeletal disorders were more common in women than in men, supported by previous literature (Buddeke et al., 2017, Marzolini et al., 2010; Foguet-Boreu et al., 2015).

Poor vision, diabetes, COPD, and asthma were statistically significantly more prevalent among all cardiovascular conditions compared to patients without the corresponding cardiovascular disease in age- and sex-adjusted analyses. This may be explained by the fact that all these diseases share risk factors similar to those of CVD. Patients with type 2 diabetes have a higher prevalence of "traditional" CVD risk factors such as dyslipidemia, abdominal obesity, smoking, and physical inactivity. Among them, diabetes is likely to be further associated with CVD through a mechanism that includes long-term hypertension, chronic hyperglycemia, microvascular disease, myocardial protein glycosylation, diabetic nephropathy, and autonomic neuropathy (Shah et al., 2015).

Likewise, COPD and CVD also share risk factors such as smoking. COPD has also been suggested to be associated with HF due to low-grade systemic inflammation, which may explain high COPD prevalence in HF patients (Hawkins et al., 2013). The poor vision was statistically significantly associated with CVD, consistent with previous studies (Christ et al., 2008; Loprinzi et al., 2015). Again, the proposed hypothesis for this association is that the conditions share risk factors, such as smoking (Christ et al., 2008). On the other hand, a previous study showed a strong association between visual impairment and 10-year risk of a first atherosclerotic event, even after adjustments for traditional risk factors (Loprinzi et al., 2015). There may exist a pathologic pathway between visual impairment and CVD, which is yet unknown. There is also a strong link between stroke and epilepsy. This finding is consistent with previous literature, showing that patients with intracerebral hemorrhage in particular have a high risk of developing epilepsy (Beghi et al., 2011).

A greater number of comorbidities was associated with higher in-hospital mortality rates. Knowledge of the full spectrum of MI comorbidities in the United States remains limited, particularly for non-cardiovascular comorbidities according to Teng et al. (2020). The most recent national hospital sample database was used, and they identified 127730 patients admitted to hospital with a MI diagnosis. Comorbidities were identified using ICD-10

in all secondary diagnoses. The most common comorbidities were found to be conventional CVD, including IHD (61.61%), followed by hyperlipidemia (58.62%), hypertension (53.97%), smoking (46.9%), diabetes mellitus type 2 (27.45%) and atrial fibrillation (19.7%). The proportion of non-cardiovascular comorbidities was significantly high. The most common comorbidities were chronic kidney disease (39.68%), anemia (24.53%), gastroesophageal reflux disease (19.78%), acute kidney injury (19.12%), COPD (13.2%), hypothyroidism (11.79%), anxiety (9.94%) and depression (8.59%).

We can conclude from the last reviewed study that MI today is associated with both conventional cardiovascular comorbidities and a high burden of non-cardiovascular comorbidities that have not been systematically investigated before. There is a need for further research on non-cardiovascular comorbidities in order to optimize the outcome of acute MI.

Recognizing the remaining gap between scientific standards and the real state of health care, a scientific team from Imperial College, UK is developing an innovative, multidisciplinary prevention program EUROACTION, coordinated by nurses, focused on families and applicable in pre-hospital and in-hospital care. The teams consisted of a coordinating nurse, nutritionist, physiotherapist, cardiologist, general practitioner, psychologist, pharmacist, etc. The main goal was to achieve a healthy lifestyle in families. 9062 patients and their families (2003-2006) participated in the study. The model has been implemented in eight European countries: England, France, Italy, Spain, Denmark, Switzerland, Holland, Poland. After one year, results show positive lifestyle changes and more effective risk factor management for participating patients and their families. The group subjected to training and monitoring by nurses showed better results regarding risk factors: smoking, healthy diet, lipid profile, blood pressure control (Kotseva et al., 2009; Kotseva et al., 2018).

The experience from EUROACTION was integrated into the national health system of England as a model for primary and secondary CVD prevention. At the same time, training of physicians, nurses and other specialists, members of the multidisciplinary teams, was carried out by creating a master's program in preventive cardiology. The study EUROACTION is an evidence-based model and recommended approach for health care across Europe (Kotseva et al., 2009).

In 2008, a new MYACTION model (Imperial College, UK) for community prevention was developed and implemented. It supports general practitioners in referring high-risk patients to appropriate preventive programs. Such pilot programs have been implemented in several UK locations. A large proportion of project participants achieved the expected target results on modifiable risk factors. The teams reported an increase in the quality of preventive interventions in primary health care

(Kotseva et al., 2009; Olisarova et al., 2019).

In 2017, according to Jennings et al., effective CVD prevention can be achieved through consolidated efforts of physicians, nurses, pharmacists, psychologists, nutritionists, and other health professionals. The most appropriate preventive care models are those that take a holistic approach to risk management (ie, encompassing all risk factors that affect the cardiovascular system), using behavioral counseling with active actions; approaches to setting goals; proven therapeutic interventions with follow-up face-to-face meetings or telephone support (2017).

Nurses are qualified to perform the following autonomous activities: to provide health information and guidance, to improve lifestyle and preventive medication, to ensure continuous patient monitoring and education. Motivating patients to adhere to therapy is the basis for positive treatment outcomes. A sufficiently effective approach is important for promotion of adherence to treatment. Good results have been achieved by sending informative telephone messages to patients. The use of an automated reminder system based on services from mobile operators is a promising approach to improve medication adherence in individuals at high risk for IHD and MI (McGorrian et al., 2011; Kolandavelu et al., 2014; Riegel et al., 2013). Patient education methods include education through written materials, CDs, mobile phone applications and monitoring. Studies show increased knowledge, though no definitive results of better self-management skills are reported. A systematic review of 33 interventions for socially significant diseases shows that knowledge is a necessary component of patient treatment, but not sufficient for effective health outcomes. Adequate self-management requires routine preventive action skills and decision-making skills in the face of deterioration. Patients report that they need practical skills to control symptoms (Beatty et al., 2013; Walters et al., 2012).

Martin et al. reported significant benefits of educating patients about self-management. A training program was used to deal with fear and anxiety, building trust in medical professionals, increasing knowledge about the disease, building skills for managing the chronic disease and dealing with accompanying mental and emotional problems. According to medical professionals, gaining control over the condition is an important goal to increase quality of life (Martin et al., 2009).

Patient education plays an important role in their active involvement in the treatment process. Experience from implementation of educational programs shows how increased knowledge of the disease affects lifestyle, and lifestyle change affects health outcomes. This new knowledge is effective both for people with insufficient health culture, as well as for health-educated persons. Educational interventions strongly influence patients' health behaviors and personal responsibility (Peterson et al., 2014).

The following effective patient education interventions are summarized. Most of the methods described are in the form of behaviorally focused trainings, structured training, monitoring to support patients' health behavior (control of therapy, blood pressure, etc.). Nursing interventions are integrated to patient needs. They take the form of telephone interviews, multimedia presentations for group learning, focus groups for case discussion and decision-making, individual meetings. Most training programs are conducted in a clinical setting followed by home visits. The training is based on the main theoretical approaches in nursing (Vaughan et al., 2017).

In Bulgaria, routine performance of preventive interventions by nurses is difficult to implement. The reasons are complex: monopoly of the Health Fund, which determines the standards of care quality; organization of work and pay of health care specialists; shortage of nurses and other specialists, low level of autonomy, lack of multidisciplinary teams, etc (Dimitrov et al., 2013).

Ivanova et al. examined the role of the qualified nurse in patient education, mitigating risk factors, and improving quality of life (2016). A significant part of the surveyed patients (48%) reported that they do not have the necessary information and skills to deal with possible complications. A need for knowledge about hygiene regime, physical activity, diet, etc. has been established (Ivanova et al., 2016). Training needs of patients with chronic diseases were analyzed in order to prevent complications and progression of the disease. Potential opportunities for nurses to educate patients in healthy living and self-care were discussed. 43.5% of the interviewees were not trained to deal with the challenges of everyday life in conditions of a chronic disease (Dobrilova et al., 2013). Cardiologists usually offer advice on diet, exercise, etc. as a part of the treatment and prevention, without providing long-term support to patients and their families. There is no effort to build partnerships between patients and medical professionals in this area. Patients expect doctors to take responsibility for their health. There is increasing talk of a health system in which patients and their families are more informed, empowered and engaged in their own health (Kireva et al., 2014; Bender et al., 2014).

CONCLUSION

High-risk heart diseases bring great harm to people's health and lives, and in recent years, this type of diseases tend to affect younger people. In order to protect people's health and improve the quality of life of patients, research in the field of treatment of cardiac diseases is very urgent and important. In the process of treating cardiac diseases, general diagnosis and therapy are certainly very important, but during this period, patient care is also essential. Effective care can help patients

improve their condition and relieve pain to a great extent. To prepare cardiology nurses as leaders in cardiovascular prevention, we must identify the specific educational and clinical competencies they need. In Bulgaria, for now, there is no regulated training for the acquisition of a cardiology nursing specialty or a CVD prevention master's program. Nurses can play a leading role in forming health culture and providing multidisciplinary preventive care. For prevention approaches to be maximally effective, they must become part of society's culture. Further research is needed to identify the factors that motivate people to engage in responsible personal health behavior.

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